

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Increased Soluble Phosphorus Loads to Lake Erie: Unintended Consequences of Conservation Practices?

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Supplemental Methods

1. Analysis of samples for total phosphorus (TP), soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP) and suspended solids (SS).

All P analyses were conducted using semi-automated colorimetric procedures (EPA, 1978), which are based on the method of Murphy and Riley (1962). Filtered (<0.45 µm) river water samples were analyzed for soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP). Unfiltered samples were analysed for total phosphorus (TP), after acid-persulfate digestion. Suspended solids were measured gravimetrically using a Whatman 934AH glass microfiber filter.

2. Stream flashiness

The Richards-Baker (R-B) Flashiness Index flashiness (Baker et al., 2004) is used here as a measure of the frequency and rapidity of short term changes in river flow, especially during runoff events, and is based on daily gauged flows. The index is calculated by dividing the path-length of flow oscillations for a time interval (i.e., the sum of the absolute values of day-to-day changes in mean daily flow) by total discharge during that time interval.

3. Estimation of the extent of tile drainage in the Sandusky, Maumee and Raisin watersheds.

Land-use/land-cover (LU/LC) and soils (SSURGO) data were imported into ARCGIS v. 10.0. These layers were then clipped to the 8 digit HUC boundaries in the WLEB, and LU/LC was limited to agricultural land uses (1. Cropland and pasture, 2. Confined feeding operations, and 3. Other agricultural land). Soils were then classified three ways to evaluate the potential necessity of tile drainage in order for the land to be used agriculturally. First, the SSURGO data provides the Hydrologic Group – Dominant Condition (hydgrpdc). Soils with hydgrpdc categories A and B were deemed to be sufficiently drained to no need supplemental drainage, while classification with a C or

D would require drainage. The second classification system was based on the hydric classification (hydclprs), with the assumption that drainage would be required in fields identified as “all hydric” or “partially hydric.” Thirdly, the soil drainage class (drclassdcd) was used to estimate the need for drainage. Using this system, the soils classified as “somewhat poorly drained,” “poorly drained,” or “very poorly drained” were assumed to need drainage to be functional agricultural land. The percentage of agricultural land in each watershed needed drainage were calculated based on the mean of these three classification systems derived from the SSURGO database.

4. Estimates of the percentage of cropland under low, medium and high residue management

Relative residue management estimates were based on the National Resource Inventory (NRI) estimates of the cover factor (C) used to calculate the Universal Soil Loss Equation (USLE). The NRI is a statistical survey of land use and natural resource conditions and trends on U.S. non-federal lands, which is undertaken every 5 years

(<http://www.nrcs.usda.gov/wps/portal/nrcs/main/national/technical/nra/nri/>). Residue management is a combination of tillage intensity, the crop rotation and the residues left by each crop. ‘Low-residue management’ would be similar to conventional tillage management, and was estimated to have a C-factor > 0.30; a ‘medium-residue management’ rating was determined to have a C-factor between 0.15 and 0.30; and ‘high-residue management’, which would include no-till and strip-till, was estimated to have a C-factor of < 0.15.

References:

EPA. 1978. Method 365.3: Phosphorous, All Forms (Colorimetric, Ascorbic Acid, Two Reagent).

https://www.epa.gov/sites/production/files/2015-08/documents/method_365-3_1978.pdf

Murphy, J., J.P. Riley. 1962. A modified single solution method for the determination of phosphate in natural-waters. *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 27: 31–36.

(a) SRP cumulative load gradients (kg-P ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)		2000	2001	2002*	2003	2004
Sandusky	1985 to reference point	0.128	0.128	0.129	0.131	0.137
	Reference point + 1 to 2014	0.434	0.448	0.456	0.458	0.461
Raisin	1985 to reference point	0.062	0.064	0.066	0.067	0.069
	Reference point + 1 to 2014	0.124	0.126	0.128	0.129	0.127
Maumee	1985 to reference point	0.164	0.165	0.168	0.171	0.177
	Reference point + 1 to 2014	0.359	0.362	0.363	0.359	0.358

(b) SRP cumulative load gradients (kg-P ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹)		1982	1983	1984*	1985	1986
Sandusky	1974 to reference point	0.298	0.291	0.298	0.294	0.285
	Reference point + 1 to 2002	0.133	0.128	0.129	0.129	0.130
Raisin	1982 to reference point	NA	0.148	0.132	0.107	0.094
	Reference point + 1 to 2002	NA	0.065	0.066	0.066	0.066
Maumee	1974 to reference point	0.353	0.350	0.342	0.329	0.313
	Reference point + 1 to 2002	0.165	0.166	0.168	0.171	0.174

Table S1 Sensitivity analysis showing the effects of changing the reference point for comparing the changes in Soluble Reactive P (SRP) cumulative load gradients, and loads, across the Sandusky, Maumee and Raisin watersheds. The mid-point years (2002* and 1984*) were chosen as common reference points for comparison of changes in cumulative load gradients across the three watersheds.

		Slope	Slope Standard Error	Intercept	Intercept Standard Error	r^2	P value	n
Sandusky	1985 to 2002	$1.987 * 10^{-3}$	$6.252 * 10^{-5}$	$1.808 * 10^{-2}$	$3.559 * 10^{-4}$	0.133	< 0.01	6574
	2003 to 2014	$3.338 * 10^{-3}$	$9.422 * 10^{-5}$	$4.244 * 10^{-2}$	$7.820 * 10^{-4}$	0.261	< 0.01	3558
Raisin	1985 to 2002	$2.187 * 10^{-3}$	$9.804 * 10^{-5}$	$1.450 * 10^{-2}$	$3.117 * 10^{-4}$	0.070	< 0.01	6574
	2003 to 2014	$3.526 * 10^{-3}$	$1.195 * 10^{-4}$	$1.191 * 10^{-2}$	$4.305 * 10^{-4}$	0.172	< 0.01	4199
Maumee	1985 to 2002	$5.095 * 10^{-4}$	$2.006 * 10^{-5}$	$3.371 * 10^{-2}$	$4.869 * 10^{-4}$	0.089	< 0.01	6574
	2003 to 2014	$8.136 * 10^{-4}$	$2.723 * 10^{-5}$	$5.241 * 10^{-2}$	$8.326 * 10^{-4}$	0.172	< 0.01	4291

Table S2 Regression models and statistics for linear regression relationships ($y = m x + c$) between daily SRP concentration and flow, where y is SRP concentration (mg-P L^{-1}) and x is flow ($\text{Mm}^3 \text{d}^{-1}$), m is the slope and c is the intercept, for the Sandusky, Raisin and Maumee watersheds, showing changes in regression relationships between (a) 1985 to 2002 and (b) 2003 to 2014.

		Coefficient of determination	Significance * 90% **95% ***99%	Observed SRP loads			Modeled SRP loads		
				Mean SRP load (kg-P d ⁻¹)	Median SRP load (kg-P d ⁻¹)	Standard deviation (kg-P d ⁻¹)	Mean SRP load (kg-P d ⁻¹)	Median SRP load (kg-P d ⁻¹)	Standard deviation (kg-P d ⁻¹)
1985-2002	Sandusky	0.968	***	112	11	316	112	17	377
	Raisin	0.991	***	51	13	113	51	19	108
	Maumee	0.839	***	743	179	1564	743	196	1777
2003-2014	Sandusky	0.925	***	399	52	946	399	54	1168
	Raisin	0.984	***	88	21	224	88	26	204
	Maumee	0.858	***	1630	315	3178	1630	337	3860

Table S3: Evaluation of SRP load model fits for the 1985-2002 and 2003-2014 datasets, and comparison of observed (measured) and modeled (predicted) daily SRP loads.

1987-2002		Cropland area (% of watershed area)	Annual P applied (kg-P ha ⁻¹ of cropland y ⁻¹)	% of annual P applied as manure	Annual P removed in crop harvest (kg-P ha ⁻¹ of cropland y ⁻¹)	P removed in crop harvest (% of annual P applied)	Cropland partial* P balance (kg-P ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹)
Sandusky	mean	79.2	19.3	7	16.1	85	3.13
	min	71.2	16.8	6	14.3	75	0.82
	max	73.6	24.1	8	18.1	95	5.99
Raisin	mean	56.6	13.9	10	14.6	110	-0.61
	min	55.0	11.6	9	12.3	65	-3.32
	max	58.5	19.1	13	16.1	128	6.75
Maumee	mean	72.3	16.7	17	15.8	96	0.97
	min	70.8	14.8	14	13.4	69	-1.81
	max	73.6	19.4	21	17.5	112	5.99
2007-2012							
Sandusky	mean	71.1	20.5	8	20.2	102	0.23
	min	70.2	15.1	6	17.5	79	-6.48
	max	72.0	27.0	10	22.4	143	5.79
Raisin	mean	54.5	12.4	8	17.2	142	-4.74
	min	53.0	10.4	6	14.2	100	-8.82
	max	55.0	16.0	10	19.2	185	-0.03
Maumee	mean	70.5	17.4	19	18.7	110	-1.38
	min	69.8	14.2	15	17.2	90	-5.27
	max	72.0	21.4	22	20.2	137	2.18

Table S4: Summary of annual cropland P inputs, P recovery by crops, and annual cropland P balance, before and after 2002. Data from IPNI, International Plant Nutrition Institute (<http://www.ipni.net/NuGIS>) (IPNI, 2012). NB summary statistics are for the years when IPNI survey data were undertaken: (a) 1987-2002: 1987, 1992, 1997, 2002; and (b) 2007-2012: 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, and 2012). *The annual cropland P balance is a *partial* balance, calculated as the difference between annual P applied (fertilizer and recoverable manure P) minus P removal in crops (see text for further details). NB these are annual summary statistics, not absolute values for individual years; therefore the partial P balance values (P applied and P removed) do not sum across the table.

		Annual P applied to land (kg-P ha ⁻¹ of watershed y ⁻¹)	Annual P removal in crop harvest (kg-P ha ⁻¹ of watershed y ⁻¹)	River annual Total P load (kg-P ha ⁻¹ of watershed y ⁻¹)	River annual Soluble Reactive P load (kg-P ha ⁻¹ of watershed y ⁻¹)	River Total P load expressed as a percentage of P applied to land (%)	River Soluble Reactive P load expressed as a percentage of P applied to land (%)	Watershed partial* P balance (kg-P ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹)
1987-2002								
Sandusky	mean	14.1	11.8	1.32	0.16	9	1.1	0.97
	min	12.3	10.5	0.70	0.11	6	0.9	-0.53
	max	17.7	13.3	1.75	0.20	13	1.4	2.66
Raisin								
	mean	7.92	8.22	0.49	0.07	7	1.0	-0.79
	min	6.49	7.22	0.28	0.04	3	0.4	-2.43
	max	11.2	9.01	0.57	0.08	9	1.2	3.67
Maumee								
	mean	12.1	11.4	1.25	0.19	11	1.6	-0.54
	min	10.9	9.82	0.42	0.09	3	0.6	-2.93
	max	14.2	12.5	1.59	0.27	15	2.4	3.98
2007-2012								
Sandusky	mean	14.5	14.4	2.05	0.46	15	3.5	-1.89
	min	10.8	12.3	1.09	0.17	6	1.3	-8.57
	max	19.2	15.8	3.94	1.02	36	9	2.99
Raisin								
	mean	6.78	9.37	0.53	0.12	8	1.9	-3.12
	min	5.69	7.76	0.19	0.05	3	0.8	-5.79
	max	8.79	10.5	0.96	0.22	17	3.9	-0.67
Maumee								
	mean	12.3	13.2	1.51	0.35	13	2.9	-2.48
	min	9.93	12.2	0.59	0.13	5	1.2	-6.22
	max	15.0	14.2	2.54	0.63	26	6.3	0.65

Table S5: Summary of annual P applications across the Sandusky, Raisin and Maumee watersheds, annual river TP and SRP loads, and the annual watershed partial P balance, before and after 2002. Data from IPNI, International Plant Nutrition Institute (<http://www.ipni.net/NuGIS>) (IPNI, 2012). NB Summary statistics for the watershed P balance, including river loads, are provided only for the years when IPNI survey data were undertaken: (a) 1987-2002: 1987, 1992, 1997, 2002; and (b) 2007-2012: 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012). * The watershed P balance is a *partial* balance, calculated as the difference between watershed P inputs from land applications and watershed P losses from river P export and crop recovery (see text for further details).

NB: Human P loadings from waste were evaluated, based on the total human P loading data for 1976-1995 (including both wastewater and sludge) presented by Baker and Richards (2002), and accounting for changes in population within the watersheds since 1995. Between 1975 and 1995, human P

loading accounted for <3% of P inputs to the Maumee and Sandusky Rivers (Baker and Richards, 2002). These human P loading estimates were based on a relatively high annual per capita loading of 2.74 kg P, compared with more recent annual per capita estimates of 0.986 kg P, which also now reflect reductions in detergent phosphate use (EPA, 2002). Between 1980 and 2010, watershed- population increased by 6% for the Maumee, but decreased by c. 5% for the Sandusky. Even taking into account the un-sewered populations within the watersheds, and assuming no transfers of human P out of the watershed (i.e., that all human waste biosolids are land applied to land with the watershed), these small demographic changes since 1995, combined with reduced per capita P loadings, mean that watershed human P loading would contribute typically less than 5% of watershed P inputs. Accordingly, these human P loadings would not have any substantial impact on watershed P balances, so are not analyzed further here.

<u>Year</u>	<u>Sandusky Residue Management</u>			<u>Raisin Residue Management</u>			<u>Maumee Residue Management</u>		
	<u>Low</u>	<u>Medium</u>	<u>High</u>	<u>Low</u>	<u>Medium</u>	<u>High</u>	<u>Low</u>	<u>Medium</u>	<u>High</u>
1982	58.3	36.5	5.2	58.4	31.1	10.5	49.5	44.5	6.1
1987	36	54.8	9.2	62.3	30.6	7.1	41.3	48.6	10.1
1992	18.2	61.8	20	57.3	30.8	11.9	30.8	43.1	26.2
1997	9.1	62.8	28.1	31.7	41	27.3	15.3	42.9	41.9
2002	11.5	44.9	43.7	25.9	37.4	36.7	12.3	39.5	48.2
2007	2.1	28.4	69.5	9.2	36.5	54.3	1.7	18.3	80.1
2012	2.1	33.9	64	14.7	27.2	58.1	3.2	26.2	70.7

Table S6. Relative residue management estimates (% of cropland under low, medium and high residue management) for the River Raisin, Maumee River and Sandusky River watersheds from 1982 to 2012.

	Sandusky	Raisin	Maumee
Gradient	$6.76 \cdot 10^{-4} (\pm 8.59 \cdot 10^{-4})$	$9.74 \cdot 10^{-6} (\pm 5.1 \cdot 10^{-4})$	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-3} (\pm 6.34 \cdot 10^{-4})$
Intercept	-0.973 (± 1.71)	+0.140 (± 1.01)	-2.055 (± 1.27)
P value	0.124	0.970	0.0007
R-B index 1984	0.3656	0.1596	0.2660
R-B index 2014	0.3879	0.1599	0.3011
Long-term (30-yr) increase in R-B index	0.0223	0.0003	0.0351
Long-term (30-year) % increase in R-B index	6.1	0.19	13.2

Table S7: Changes in Richards-Baker (R-B) Flashiness Index (Baker et al, 2004) for the Sandusky, Raisin and Maumee Rivers (see Fig SI4, and SI Methods)

Fig S1 Map of the Maumee, Raisin and Sandusky watersheds draining into the Western basin of Lake Erie, and the location of river water quality monitoring stations

Fig S2: Cumulative load time-series for Soluble Reactive Phosphorus (SRP) in the Sandusky, Raisin and Maumee watersheds. The blue broken lines denote major changes in gradient of SRP load accumulation.

Fig S3a: Temporal patterns in the acreage of major crops (corn, soybeans and wheat), and in total, rural and urban human population in the Sandusky, Maumee and Raisin watersheds. Agricultural census data from <https://www.agcensus.usda.gov/>. NB: Between 1987 and 2012, there were small increases (c. 10% or less) in area of soybean in all three watersheds; increases in area of corn of 12% and 16% in the Sandusky and Maumee, but a 4% reduction in corn in the Raisin; and reductions in the area of wheat of 13%, 33% and 43% in the Raisin, Sandusky and Maumee, respectively. Population data were accessed from <http://www.census.gov/popest/data/index.html>

Fig S3b: Temporal patterns in animal numbers in the three states of the Western Lake Erie Basin (Ohio, Indiana and Michigan). Note that manure generally accounts for less than 20% of applied P in the WLEB (see Table S14). Livestock numbers were accessed from <https://www.agcensus.usda.gov/>

Fig S4: Temporal patterns in the Richards-Baker Flashiness Index for the Maumee, Sandusky and Raisin Rivers (with a long-term linear regression line fitted to the data - see Table SI7 for regression statistics).

Fig S15 Time-series of (a) annual flow-weighted mean soluble reactive P concentrations, (b) annual flow-weighted mean total P concentrations, and (c) annual mean flows for the Sandusky River, 1985 to 2013.